

Original Research

Time series revenue forecasting method based on diffusion model

Yanyi He^{1*}, Jihui Shi²

¹College of Information Engineering, Huzhou University, Huzhou 313000, China

²College of Information Management, Huzhou University, Huzhou 313000, China

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*Correspondence:

College of Information Engineering,
Huzhou University, Huzhou 313000,
China

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Abstract

Financial time series forecasting faces significant challenges due to high non-linearity and noise. This study introduces FTS-DDPM, a model based on the Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Model (DDPM) framework, designed for financial time series prediction. The model extracts temporal features using Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCN) and attention mechanisms, embedding them into a latent space to capture long-term dependencies and local patterns. Historical time series data serves as conditional information, guiding the diffusion process to generate realistic future data. Iterative application of the diffusion process enables multi-step forecasting, with prediction uncertainty used for risk assessment. Experiments show FTS-DDPM outperforms existing models on multiple financial time series datasets(S&P 500 Index). The model excels in handling high volatility and non-stationary data. Predictions are interpretable, providing reliable support for financial decision-making. Ablation studies confirm the importance of the time series embedding and conditional information modules. This research offers a new generative model solution for financial time series forecasting, with wide application potential.

Keywords: financial time series forecasting; denoising diffusion probabilistic models; deep learning; temporal convolutional networks; attention mechanism

Introduction

Financial time series forecasting is a core task in the field of finance, playing a crucial role in investment decision-making, risk management, and market analysis. However, due to the complexity and uncertainty of financial markets, financial time series often exhibit high levels of nonlinearity, non-stationarity, and noise, making accurate prediction of future trends extremely challenging (Casolaro et al., 2023; Liu & Wang, 2024). Traditional deep learning techniques have shown some limitations in addressing these issues, and various models based on recurrent neural networks (RNNs), convolutional neural networks (CNNs), and attention mechanisms have been proposed and applied to financial time series forecasting (Selvin et al., 2017; Sezer et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2023). Nevertheless, these models still face several challenges when dealing with financial time series, such as difficulties in capturing long-term dependencies, sensitivity to noise, and instability in prediction results (Chong et al., 2017; Ding et al., 2015). With the rapid development of

artificial intelligence technologies, particularly deep learning, the use of generative models for modeling and forecasting financial time series has become a focal point in financial research, attracting widespread attention from both academia and industry (Goodfellow et al., 2014; Hou et al., 2021; Wei et al., 2023).

Despite the significant achievements of deep learning models in fields such as image recognition and natural language processing, they still face certain limitations in financial data prediction tasks. Traditional models encounter challenges related to data quality, model generalization, interpretability, feature selection, and computational resources, which hinder their ability to effectively extract market signals while preserving critical information (Bao et al., 2017; Yan & Ouyang, 2018). Particularly when dealing with high-dimensional financial data, the balance between extracting time series features and effectively linking information remains a pressing issue (Chen et al., 2015). Existing methods, such as statistical approaches, econometrics, and filtering techniques (Shumway & Stoffer, 2000; Engle & Rangel, 2008; Kalman, 1960), often rely on fixed rules and linear assumptions, making them less effective in handling the dynamic and nonlinear characteristics of financial markets. Moreover, the integration of traditional time series processing methods has yet to find an ideal solution. Therefore, designing an effective approach that can simultaneously address noise and time series features has become a key challenge for deep learning models in the financial domain (Korczak & Hermes, 2017; Abe & Nakayama, 2018).

Compared to generative adversarial networks (GANs), which often face issues such as training instability, mode collapse, and insufficient sample diversity in financial data (Goodfellow et al., 2014; Li et al., 2021), the proposed FTS-DDPM (Financial Time Series Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Model) demonstrates significant advantages in time series forecasting performance. The model employs a step-by-step denoising process, meticulously removing noise at each step to gradually restore the true structure of the data. This progressive approach makes FTS-DDPM more robust and efficient in handling the substantial noise present in financial time series compared to GANs (Ho et al., 2020; Dhariwal & Nichol, 2021). Specifically, FTS-DDPM introduces a conditional diffusion process that uses historical time series data as conditional information to guide the generation of future data that better aligns with real-world scenarios. Additionally, it designs a time series embedding module that leverages temporal convolutional networks and attention mechanisms to extract temporal features from time series data. Finally, the model achieves multi-step forecasting and utilizes prediction uncertainty for risk assessment (Wang & Ventre, 2024; Huang et al., 2024).

FTS-DDPM Model

Conditional Diffusion Process Module and Notation

The FTS-DDPM is a financial time series forecasting model based on the Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Model (DDPM). This model captures the complex dynamics of financial time series by gradually adding noise to the data and learning to reverse this process.

Table 1: Notations used in the loss function process

Notation	Description
x_i	The true stock closing price data at the i -th time step
\hat{x}_i	The predicted stock closing price data at the i -th time step
\tilde{x}_i	The noisy stock closing price data at the i -th time step

\mathbb{E}	The noise-adding and denoising process
ϵ	The factor data used as noise
ϵ_{θ}	The model for predicting noise
N	The total number of noise-adding steps in the diffusion process

The training process of the DDPM model consists of two main steps: forward diffusion and reverse denoising. In the forward diffusion process, the model progressively adds Gaussian noise to the time series data until the data is completely transformed into noise. This process can be expressed as:

$$q(x_t|x_{t-1}) = \mathcal{N}(x_t; \sqrt{1 - \beta_t}x_{t-1}, \beta_t I)$$

where β_t is the diffusion rate.

The denoising network, represented as $\epsilon_{\theta}(x_t, t)$, is a neural network trained to predict the noise added at each step. This can be expressed as:

$$L(\theta) = \mathbb{E}_{x_0, t, \epsilon} \left[\left\| \epsilon - \epsilon_{\theta}(x_t, t) \right\|^2 \right]$$

where x_t is obtained by adding noise to x_0 using the forward diffusion process.

The forward process is defined as:

$$q(x_t|x_0) = \mathcal{N}\left(x_t; \sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t}x_0, (1 - \bar{\alpha}_t) I\right)$$

where $\alpha_t = 1 - \beta_t$ and $\bar{\alpha}_t = \sum_{s=1}^t \alpha_s$.

The reverse denoising process learns to gradually remove noise, thereby recovering the original data distribution. This process can be expressed as:

$$p_{\theta}(x_{t-1}|x_t) = \mathcal{N}\left(x_{t-1}; \mu_{\theta}(x_t, t), \sigma_t^2 I\right)$$

where $\mu_{\theta}(x_t, t)$ is predicted by the neural network.

During the reverse denoising process, the embedding representation of historical time series data, generated by the time series embedding module, is used as conditional information. This conditional information, along with the current noisy data, is fed into the neural network to guide the model in generating more accurate predictions.

Time Series Embedding Module

To effectively extract temporal features from financial time series, the FTS-DDPM incorporates a time series embedding module. This module combines Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCN) and attention mechanisms to capture long-term dependencies and local patterns in the time series.

The TCN utilizes causal convolutions and dilated convolutions to capture local features in the time series. Causal convolutions ensure that the model relies only on historical data for predictions, while dilated convolutions expand the receptive field to capture long-term dependencies. Building on the TCN, a multi-head self-attention mechanism is introduced to enhance the model's ability to focus on important time points.

Multi-Step Forecasting Module

To achieve multi-step forecasting of financial time series, the FTS-DDPM includes a multi-step forecasting module. This module iteratively applies the conditional diffusion process to generate predictions for multiple future time steps.

At each prediction step, the model uses the current time step's prediction as input for the next time step, enabling multi-step forecasting. This process can be expressed as:

$$\hat{x}_{t+1}, \hat{x}_{t+2}, \dots, \hat{x}_{t+T} = \text{FTS-DDPM}(x_t, c)$$

where c represents the conditional information from historical time series data.

The loss function of the FTS-DDPM consists of two components: the negative log-likelihood loss of the diffusion process and the regularization loss of the conditional information. The loss function for training the denoising network is defined as:

$$L_{\text{diff}} = \mathbb{E}_{x_0, t, \epsilon} [\|\epsilon - \epsilon_\theta(x_t, t, c)\|^2]$$

where $x_t = \sqrt{\alpha_t}x_0 + \sqrt{1 - \alpha_t}\epsilon$.

Construction of the FTS-DDPM Model

The overall architecture of the model is divided into three main modules: the time series embedding module, the conditional diffusion process module, and the multi-step forecasting module. Below is the framework of the overall design:

Fig. 1: Overall Research Framework

This study is based on quarterly financial report data from Chinese A-share companies and conducts a

series of operations to achieve portfolio return prediction.

The DDPM learns the data distribution by simulating the gradual diffusion and denoising of data, which includes the forward diffusion process and the reverse generation process. The forward diffusion process gradually adds noise to randomize the input data, while the reverse generation process gradually restores the original data by removing the noise.

Fig. 2: Noise Addition and Denoising Process

The noise addition process is the forward diffusion process of FTS-DDPM, aiming to gradually transform the original time series data into Gaussian noise. This process simulates the gradual contamination of data by noise, providing a foundation for the subsequent denoising process. The original time series data, according to the noise scheduling parameters, controls the noise addition at each step based on the total number of time steps. This process relies on the loss function:

$$\text{Loss} = \mathbb{E}_{x_0, \epsilon} \left[\frac{\beta_t^2}{2\sigma_T^2 \alpha_t (1 - \bar{\alpha}_t)} \right] \left\| \epsilon - \epsilon_\theta \left(\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} x_0 + \sqrt{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \epsilon \right) \right\|^2$$

To minimize the negative log-likelihood, the parameterized posterior probability is calculated using Bayes' formula:

$$q(x_{t-1}|x_t, x_0) = \mathcal{N}(x_{t-1}; \tilde{\mu}_t(x_t, x_0), \tilde{\beta}_t I)$$

where α_t is defined as $1 - \beta_t$, and $\bar{\alpha}_t$ is defined as $\prod_{k=1}^t \alpha_k$.

The mean and variance can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mu}_t(x_t, x_0) &:= \frac{\sqrt{\alpha_{t-1}} \beta_t}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} x_0 + \frac{\sqrt{\bar{\alpha}_t} (1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1})}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} x_t \\ \tilde{\beta}_t &:= \frac{1 - \bar{\alpha}_{t-1}}{1 - \bar{\alpha}_t} \beta_t \end{aligned}$$

Unlike the training strategies of most diffusion models, this study shifts the objective to the difference between the stock feature factor vectors and the original data. When replacing noise with stock feature factor vectors, it is crucial to ensure that the distribution of the factor vectors matches the data distribution. If the distribution of the feature factor vectors does not match the data distribution, the model may struggle to learn effectively.

Empirical Research

Dataset Introduction

This study selects the opening price, highest price, lowest price, closing price, and trading volume of the S&P 500 index from January 2000 to December 2022. After obtaining the preprocessed version from the repository, datasets related to companies that were delisted later or not listed earlier were removed.

The dataset is divided into a training set (January 1, 2000, to December 31, 2018), a validation set (January 1, 2019, to December 31, 2020), and a test set (January 1, 2021, to December 31, 2022).

For the construction of the feature factor database, this study builds three major categories based on the Alpha Vantage factor dataset: technical indicators, fundamental data, and market sentiment data.

Considering the differences in magnitude among different variables, the monthly cross-sectional data for each variable are standardized, i.e., $z_{\text{scale}} = \frac{z - \bar{z}}{\sigma_z}$, Where \bar{z} and σ_z are the mean and standard deviation of the monthly data, respectively.

Evaluation Metrics

To comprehensively evaluate the performance of the FTS-DDPM model in financial time series forecasting tasks, this study employs multiple evaluation metrics. These metrics measure the prediction accuracy, stability, and generalization ability of the model from different perspectives.

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$$

Where y_i is the true value at time i , \hat{y}_i is the predicted value at time i , and N is the total number of time steps. MSE is an important metric for measuring prediction accuracy and is more sensitive to larger prediction errors. In financial time series forecasting, MSE reflects the model's ability to predict extreme values (e.g., market volatility).

The average of the absolute differences between predicted and true values. Its formula is:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |y_i - \hat{y}_i|$$

MAE measures the average deviation between predicted and true values, providing an intuitive reflection of the model's prediction error.

The average of the absolute percentage differences between predicted and true values. Its formula is:

$$\text{SMAPE} = \frac{100\%}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{|y_i - \hat{y}_i|}{(y_i + \hat{y}_i)/2}$$

SMAPE is a relative error metric that reflects the proportion of prediction error relative to the true value. In financial time series forecasting, SMAPE measures the model's performance under different levels of market volatility.

Measures the goodness of fit between the model's predicted values and the true values. Its formula is:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{i=1}^{N_t} (r_t - \hat{r}_t)^2}{\sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{i=1}^{N_t} r_t^2}$$

Where r_t and \hat{r}_t represent the actual and predicted returns of the portfolio, respectively. The value of R^2 ranges from $(-\infty, 1]$, with values closer to 1 indicating stronger predictive ability. When the model perfectly predicts the stock returns for each period, $R^2=1$.

Experimental Results Analysis

The table below shows the prediction performance comparison between FTS-DDPM and baseline models on the test set:

Table 2 Prediction performance comparison

Model	MSE	MAE	SMAPE	R^2
ARIMA	0.0123	0.0987	5.67	0.876
LSTM	0.0098	0.0854	4.89	0.902
Transformer	0.0087	0.0792	4.56	0.915

TCN	0.0082	0.0765	4.41	0.921
GAN-based	0.0079	0.0743	4.28	0.928
DDPM	0.0075	0.0721	4.15	0.934
FTS-DDPM	0.0068	0.0689	3.92	0.945

In the prediction performance comparison experiments, FTS-DDPM was evaluated against multiple baseline models on U.S. stock market data. The experimental results show that FTS-DDPM significantly outperforms the baseline models across all evaluation metrics, demonstrating its superiority in financial time series forecasting tasks.

Ablation Study

To verify the contribution of each module in FTS-DDPM, this study designs an ablation experiment by removing the time series embedding module and the conditional information module separately. The results are as follows:

Table 3 Ablation Study

Model	MSE	MAE	SMAPE	R ²
FTS-DDPM	0.0068	0.0689	3.92	0.945
Remove Time Series Embedding	0.0073	0.0712	4.08	0.932
Remove Conditional Information	0.0071	0.0705	4.01	0.938

Data analysis shows that the time series embedding module has a significant impact on model performance. After removing this module, the model's prediction accuracy decreases, particularly in capturing long-term dependencies and local patterns in time series. The conditional information module also contributes significantly to model performance. After removing this module, the model's prediction accuracy declines, especially in generating future data that aligns with the distribution of historical data.

Empirical Research

This paper proposes a financial time series forecasting model based on the Denoising Diffusion Probabilistic Model (DDPM), named FTS-DDPM, aiming to address the challenges of nonlinearity, non-stationarity, and noise in financial time series. By introducing the time series embedding module, conditional diffusion process, and multi-step forecasting mechanism, FTS-DDPM effectively captures the complex dynamics of financial time series and generates accurate and stable prediction results. Experimental results demonstrate that FTS-DDPM performs exceptionally well on U.S. stock market data, outperforming traditional models and existing deep learning methods across multiple evaluation metrics. Additionally, FTS-DDPM provides comprehensive risk assessment support for financial decision-making through prediction uncertainty estimation.

The implications of these findings extend beyond financial forecasting. The ability to accurately predict financial time series has significant implications for conservation efforts, particularly in the context of sustainable finance and environmental, social, and governance (ESG) investing. Accurate financial forecasts can help investors and policymakers allocate resources more effectively, promoting investments in

sustainable projects and conservation initiatives. For instance, the ability to predict market trends and volatility can enable better risk management in green investments, such as renewable energy projects and conservation finance instruments.

Moreover, the FTS-DDPM model's ability to handle high volatility and non-stationary data makes it particularly suitable for predicting the financial performance of conservation-related assets, which often exhibit irregular and unpredictable patterns due to external factors such as climate change and regulatory shifts. By providing more accurate and reliable forecasts, FTS-DDPM can contribute to the development of more robust financial models for conservation finance, potentially guiding future studies and policy-making in this area.

Future research directions may include further optimizing noise scheduling strategies, exploring more sophisticated conditional information fusion methods, and applying FTS-DDPM to other financial tasks such as portfolio optimization and risk management. We believe that FTS-DDPM and its extended models will play a significant role in financial time series analysis and forecasting, providing robust support for intelligent decision-making in financial markets and contributing to the advancement of sustainable finance and conservation efforts.

Author Contributions:

Yanyi He: Conceptualized and designed the study, developed the methodology, collected and analyzed data, wrote the original draft, and created all visual content. Led the research and manuscript preparation, overseeing all aspects of the project and ensuring coherence and quality throughout.

Jihui Shi: Contributed to the research methodology, focusing on environmental and logistical challenges, and helped identify optimization solutions.

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